

METHODS OF TEACHING THE MOTHER TONGUE IN GENERAL SECONDARY EDUCATION AND THEIR INTERPRETATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20806263>

Abstract. *It is known that the effectiveness of the educational process depends on its organization on the basis of cooperation between the teacher and learners, on the full consideration of learners’ abilities within this cooperation, and on the correct selection of techniques, methods, and tools that activate learners.*

Keywords: *teacher and learners, techniques, methods, practical techniques: various types of exercises and practical work.*

INTRODUCTION

It is known that the effectiveness of the educational process depends on its organization on the basis of cooperation between the teacher and learners, on the full consideration of learners’ abilities within this cooperation, and on the correct selection of techniques, methods, and tools that activate learners.

The Concept of Teaching the Mother Tongue in General Secondary Education states that, “based on the main direction, aim, tasks, content, and principles of teaching the Uzbek language, and taking into account the latest achievements of linguistics and methodology, it is necessary to select from them those that correspond to learners’ life needs and thereby effectively organize Uzbek language education in educational institutions and raise it to a new stage in terms of practical effectiveness.”¹ This requirement calls for a particularly responsible approach to teaching the mother tongue.

METHODS

Based on the explanations of teaching techniques given in A. G‘ulomov and M. Qodirov’s textbook *Methodology of Teaching the Mother Tongue*² and in B. To‘xliyev, M. Shamsiyeva, and T. Ziyodova’s textbook *Methodology of Teaching the Uzbek Language*,³ it is appropriate to state that a teaching technique⁴ is a detail or component of a method, a type of practical activity directed toward independent thinking and serving to ensure the acquisition of knowledge and skills.

A method specifies the nature and direction of learning activity, whereas a technique is the teacher’s concrete action. According to the organization of joint activity between the teacher and students, the following techniques are distinguished: conversation, explanation, and independent work.

On the basis of sources of knowledge, the following techniques are distinguished:

observation and analysis of language material, such as phonetic analysis, lexical analysis, and grammatical analysis;

visual⁵ observation (observing or seeing an object or event with the eyes or with binoculars), experimentation, and observation;

practical techniques: various types of exercises and practical work.

In methodological literature, the teacher's oral delivery of information to students, that is, the teacher's living word, lecture, and explanation, is being included both as a technique and as a method.

Teaching techniques are a complex process that requires alternation during the teaching of a topic. To this day, among methodologist scholars who deal with this issue, there are cases where "method" and "technique" are used without distinction. No single solution has been reached in understanding and interpreting the essence of this pedagogical category. The fact is that, despite the considerable attention paid to this problem, duality in views still persists. Developing samples for teaching topics on the basis of the diversity of techniques and the consistency of their application within a certain system, and recommending them to school education, helps to organize the activity of practicing teachers correctly. Thus, the following conclusion may be drawn about the evolution of teaching techniques: 1. No single technique can fully ensure the required results. 2. Good results can be achieved only through different techniques. 3. The greatest effect can be achieved through the use of mutually complementary techniques that form a system, rather than through techniques that are multidirectional and unrelated. This raises the question of what a technique is and in what situations it is applied. We consider it appropriate to answer this question as follows:

1. A technique is not the activity itself, but the way of carrying it out. In practice, it turns into a technique.
2. A technique itself should not be considered wrong; only its application may be wrong. When applying a technique, all its requirements must be observed.
3. Each technique has its own specific subject, and each of them is a unique procedure.
4. A technique always belongs to the actor: the teacher recommends, and the student performs; the student is the actor. According to M. M. Levina, there is no activity without an object and no technique without activity. Any technique is applied in the educational process, or different techniques exist within different actions; techniques are not limited only to education.
5. The educational process must awaken in the child an intense inner desire for knowledge and vigorous mental work. The success of the entire educational process largely depends on the choice of the techniques applied.

The teaching technique is chosen by the teacher. In doing so, the teacher must follow a number of requirements.

RESULTS

A teaching technique is the orderly activity of the teacher and students aimed at achieving a given educational objective. Teaching techniques, in the didactic sense, are often understood as a set of ways to achieve goals and solve educational problems. In pedagogical literature, the concept of method is sometimes discussed only in relation to the teacher's activity or only in relation to students' activity. In the first case, it is appropriate to speak about teaching techniques. If the joint work of the teacher and students is meant, then teaching techniques are undoubtedly manifested. K. D. Ushinsky has a well-known statement: "The nature of children requires clear visibility. Teach a child five unfamiliar words, and he will suffer over them in vain for a long time; but connect twenty such words with pictures, and the child will learn them in an instant. You explain a very simple idea to a child and he does not understand you; explain difficult information to the same child on the basis of a picture, and he understands you quickly ... If you show pictures, the class begins to speak." Therefore, various techniques are important in a person's comprehension and knowledge of all things. A technique is directly connected with the aims and

tasks of the lesson. Techniques are determined, first of all, by the effectiveness of teaching and learning methods. In general, a technique is called a way or a system of techniques by means of which a certain goal is achieved in the performance of a particular process. Thus, in determining the essence of a technique, two characteristic features can be identified. First, there is the feature of the goal-oriented nature of the action; second, there is the feature of its regulation. These may be called the standard characteristics of a general technique. However, there are also characteristics that are specific only to teaching techniques. These include, first of all: certain forms of cognitive activity; any means of information exchange between teachers and students; stimulation of students' learning and cognitive activity; control of the educational process; management of students' cognitive activity; and revealing the content of knowledge in an educational institution.

Therefore, attention must be focused specifically on the cognitive aspect of students. The age-related developmental characteristics of cognitive processes such as sensation, perception, memory, thinking, speech, imagination, and representation constitute the basis for mastering education.

The diversity of teaching techniques and their application in a definite sequence ensure the effectiveness of teachers' educational activity. The technique is chosen by the teacher. Teaching techniques may be summarized as follows: 1. No single technique can fully ensure the expected result. 2. Expected results require a set of techniques that direct learners toward mental activity. 3. The effectiveness of learning and cognitive activity is achieved through the use of systematic techniques that are connected with one another. The effectiveness of techniques depends on the following:

6. A technique must serve as a way of carrying out learning activity.
7. Through each technique, a particular feature of the topic must be identified and revealed. Each technique must be directed toward its own task.
8. The teacher chooses the technique; a correctly chosen technique guarantees that the student's activity will be directed properly. The teacher recommends, and the student performs.

As M. M. Levina emphasizes, there is no activity without an object and no technique without activity. Any technique is applied in the educational process, or different actions are carried out through different techniques.

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In pedagogical literature, the concepts of method and technique are sometimes given the same explanation. During a lesson, sometimes only the activity of the teacher or only the activity of students is discussed. In the educational process, the activity of the teacher and the student is united by the teaching technique and the method. A teaching method consists of a set of teaching techniques. If the joint work of the teacher and students is meant, teaching techniques are certainly manifested. K. D. Ushinsky has a well-known statement:

"The nature of children requires clear visibility. Teach a child five unfamiliar words, and he will suffer over them in vain for a long time; but connect twenty such words with pictures, and the child will learn them in an instant ..."

Thus, through various techniques, a person can understand and know everything. A technique must correspond directly to the aims and tasks of the lesson. With the help of techniques, a certain process is carried out, and this process ensures the achievement of the goal. In a set of techniques, each selected technique must have its own independent feature, function, and definite

order in achieving the intended goal. A teaching technique is characterized by its service to: a) certain forms of cognitive activity; b) a means of information exchange between the teacher and students; c) stimulation of students' learning and cognitive activity; d) control of the educational process; e) management of students' cognitive activity; and f) revealing the content of knowledge in an educational institution. The selected techniques ensure educational effectiveness through their ability to develop students' cognitive processes such as sensation, perception, memory, thinking, speech, imagination, and representation.

International integration in the field of education and the introduction of advanced foreign teaching and assessment techniques into national education have created opportunities to achieve teaching effectiveness.

DISCUSSION

One of the interactive techniques, the "Cluster" technique, is being referred to both as a method and as a technology. The word cluster means "bud" or "bundle." The Cluster technique is a structure that enables thinking about the relationships among various ideas. This technique ensures that students thoroughly master the topic. The "Cluster" technique may be used both for individual work with students and for group work. Each group of students is given tasks to complete independently.

With the help of "Cluster" technology, the internal parts of the phenomenon being studied and the divisions among them are clarified. For example, using "Cluster" technology to classify "word classes" according to their similar and different features ensures students' conscious thinking. Text analysis is carried out with students on the basis of the following tasks.

Text: The Moon is the celestial body closest to the Earth. It is four times smaller than the Earth, and its weight is 81 times less.

The Moon completes a full orbit around the Earth in one day and night. When viewed from the Earth, the Moon appears differently at different times.

The Moon also has mountains and plains similar to those on the Earth. However, there is no layer of air and no water, and for this reason many celestial bodies strike it. As a result, sloping craters have formed on the surface of the Moon. One of them is named after Ulugbek. There are dark spots on the surface of the Moon. They are called "seas." However, there is no trace of water in these "seas." (M. Mirakmalov)

Task 1. Read the text. Group the words on the basis of questions. Identify the words that do not answer any question on their own.

What? — Moon, Earth, sky, body, day and night, mountain, ...

Who? — Ulugbek, ...

Who? (plural) — they,

What does it do? — appears, ... What kind? — dark, ...

How many? — four, eighty-one, ...

Which? — this,

Words that do not answer a question on their own: esa, bor, yo‘q, lekin, va, ham, and so on.

Task 2. Think. What word class would you give to the words that answer questions? What would you call the words that do not answer questions?

On the basis of their previous knowledge, students name them as nouns, adjectives, numerals, and verbs.

Task 3. Read the sentences by omitting the words *lekin* and *bilan*. Say what purpose these words serve. Say what purpose the word *ham* serves.

A “Cluster” is formed on the basis of students’ answers. On the basis of the cluster, students’ opinions are heard about the principles used in classifying words into word classes, as well as their answers to the question: “How did the Cluster technology affect your mastery of knowledge?”

One of the methods created under the many abbreviations in Lean terminology (free translation), such as 4K, 5W+H, 3M, 7W, and others, is 5M. It is being applied to the field of mother tongue teaching, and experimental results are being noted as successful. Today, 5M technology also makes it possible to achieve good results in the field of education. Each component of this abbreviation is expressed under separate numbers, and students’ activity is organized on the basis of 5M technology:

1M — human, person (English: man; in education, a student or students).

2M — educational tools necessary in the educational process (car/machine, equipment).

3M — learning materials (materials).

4M — time allocated for learning activity (measure).

5M — method (method — way, technique).

Each abbreviation “M” given under the numbers describes the learning material necessary for organizing the activity of the student and the teacher, the time spent on teaching, and effective teaching methods and techniques. There are two situations in the use of these abbreviations, that is, they are classical tools used to analyze the causes of a problem. For example, using this technology gives good results in classifying lexical units according to meaning and form and in explaining the educational and pedagogical importance of studying historical and archaic words. Students are assigned the task of identifying and explaining historical and archaic words used in the historical works of Uzbek writers and writers of related peoples and of justifying their significance. For example, Abay’s Book of Words, Chingiz Aitmatov’s *The Day Lasts More Than a Hundred Years*, and Oybek’s *Kutlug‘ Qon* are recommended. Students are asked to identify historical lexical units used in the languages of the related Kazakh, Kyrgyz, and Uzbek peoples; to identify, classify, and explain the historical and archaic lexical units common to these peoples’ languages; to classify and explain the historical and archaic lexical units specific to each people’s language; to write the identified lexemes on separate cards; and to indicate on each card the source, author, title of the work, publisher, and page. Students understand that historical and archaic words reflect the origins of Turkic peoples and their separate paths of development in the lexicon of their languages. They also come to realize that the lexicon of the Uzbek language has broad possibilities for expressing thought.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, methods and innovative technologies such as associative series, supporting reminders, additions, brainstorming, group discussion, clusters, synchronization (aligning language phenomena with one another), essays, didactic games, and learning concepts through text analysis make it possible to achieve effective results in teaching the mother tongue. The demands being placed on the current educational process create a need to use world experience.

REFERENCES

1. Concept of Teaching the Mother Tongue in General Secondary Education. Tashkent, 2020.
2. State Educational Standard and Curriculum of General Secondary Education. Tashkent, 2020.

3. G'ulomov A., Qodirov M., et al. Methodology of Teaching the Mother Tongue. Tashkent, 2012.
4. To'xliyev B., Shamsiyeva M., Ziyodova T. Methodology of Teaching the Uzbek Language. Publishing House of the Literature Fund of the Writers' Union of Uzbekistan. Tashkent, 2006.